

**EVOLUTION OF COOPERATION OF STATES IN THE FIGHT
AGAINST TRANSNATIONAL CRIME IN THE FIELD OF
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES****Jonuzokova Yulduz**

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The history of cooperation between countries in the fight against transnational crime in the field of information technologies begins when the Internet became widely available and became an important tool for communication, business, and remote services. Development and modernity of the Internet together with the fact that information and communication technologies provide many opportunities, created conditions for various forms of crimes in the field of information technologies.

In today's era of globalization, crimes in the field of information technology go beyond the borders of national states and cause great damage to the economies of the countries of the world. At the same time, crimes in this area are committed in various ways and methods, making their detection even more difficult. The complexity of the detection of crimes and the fact that they do not know borders require interstate cooperation against crimes committed in this area.

The first international initiative on crimes in the field of information technologies, especially computer crimes, was put forward in Strasbourg in 1976 at the Conference of the Council of Europe on Criminological Aspects of Economic Crime. Methodological aspects of phenomenological research on economic crime, its goals and problems will be discussed at the first session of this conference. Also, although attention was paid to the definition of various crimes and the improvement of methods of combating them, several categories of computer crimes were introduced at this meeting.¹

Interpol for the first time in 1979 at a conference held in Paris put forward the initiative of the need to pay attention to the issue of computer crime and criminal law.² At the conference, an opinion on computer fraud was expressed, and it was noted that due to the constantly growing communication between different countries by telephone, satellite and other means, computer crime is

¹ A Paper for the 12th Conference of Directors of Criminological Research Institutes: Criminological Aspects of Economic Crime, Strasbourg, 15-18 November 1976, page 225-229.

² The Third Interpol Symposium on International Fraud, Saint-Cloud, Paris, France, December 11-13, 1979.

becoming international in nature. In this situation, it is emphasized that Interpol and other similar international organizations should pay more attention to this aspect.³

Later, Interpol's computer crime project was approved by the UN General Assembly in 1980. Interpol sends a survey on computer crime to member countries.⁴

The first Interpol training seminar for computer crime investigators was held in Paris on December 7-11, 1981.⁵

In conjunction with this conference, the following areas of unsatisfactory legislation on computer crime and criminal law of Interpol member countries will be identified:

- change and destroy data or otherwise influence data processing for destructive purposes;
- acquiring or obtaining relevant information for the purpose of exposing a crime;
- obtaining computer services for one's own purpose without authorization using the appropriate computer;
- changing data with the intention of using it in fraudulent or legal transactions;

It was the first step in development. It is also emphasized that the criminal code should be harmonized through the guidelines and recommendations developed in interstate cooperation in order to improve the fight against transnational crime in the field of information technologies. Otherwise, it is concluded that problems of international jurisdiction can be avoided.

In 1982, in Paris, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development decided to appoint a committee of 21 experts to discuss computer-related crimes and the need to amend the Criminal Code. Later, as a result of the proposals of this expert committee, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development in 1986 decided on the need for international cooperation, taking into account the transnational aspects of computer-related criminal activity, and the need for all member states to reflect the actions committed in this area in their national criminal legislation. gives recommendations.⁶

³ Stein Schjolberg, then Assistant Commissioner of Police in Oslo, Norway.

⁴ Approved by Secretary General A. Bossard on April 30, 1980

⁵ The Conference was organized by Interpol in co-operation with Stein Schjolberg, It was attended by 66 delegates from 26 countries. The keynote speaker at the Conference was Donn B. Parker, SRI International, Menlo Park, California, USA, the "founder" of the combat against computer crime.

⁶ Stein Schjolberg: EDP and Penal Legislation, A presentation at the Interpol Conference in December 1981. In cooperation with SRI International, USA, The Norwegian Research Center for Computers and Law, University of Oslo, and Interpol, Paris, he was working on a model law for computer crime laws that could be used as a remedy, or guideline for other countries.

In 1985, the Council of Europe appointed an expert committee to discuss the legal issues of computer-related crimes. The expert group develops proposals for improving the legislation on combating crime in the field of information technologies. Recommendations include conduct such as computer fraud, falsification of information, damage to computer data or computer programs, computer sabotage, and unauthorized access.

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